

EFFECTIVE ELASTIC MODULI AND FIELDS DUE TO UNIAXIAL TENSILE TRACTION IN A PARTICULATE COMPOSITE BY THE THREE PHASE MODEL

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ABSTRACT: Effective elastic constants of a particulate composite and stress fields developed in it under a uniaxial tensile load are derived by using the three phase model. Isotropic elastic spherical inclusions embedded in an isotropic elastic matrix are replaced by a spherical inclusion enclosed in a spherical matrix, and the composite sphere is surrounded by an infinite homogeneous isotropic elastic body whose elastic constants equal the effective elastic moduli of the given particulate composite. The boundary of the infinite body is subjected to either a state of uniform hydrostatic pressure or uniform uniaxial tensile tractions. Closed form solutions for stresses and strains in the spherical inclusion, the matrix, and the effective medium are derived. By requiring that under the same applied surface tractions, an infinite linear elastic isotropic homogeneous body with moduli equal to the effective elastic moduli of the given particulate composite has the same strain energy as the aforesaid three phase body, we find effective elastic properties of the particulate composite. These properties are found to compare well with test findings and also with those computed by using other methods. For low volume fraction of inclusions, stresses developed at the interface between the inclusion and the matrix agree well with those for a single inclusion in an infinite medium.

KEYWORDS: Particulate composite, spherical inclusions, three-phase model, effective elastic properties.

INTRODUCTION

Successful practical applications of new materials require a knowledge of their mechanical properties and sources of stress concentrations. A polymer matrix particulate composite under tensile loads generally fails due to dewetting of inclusions followed by plastic deformations that result in crazing and shear band formation. Tensile tests on polymeric composites with perfectly bonded spherical glass inclusions have revealed that crazes form near the poles of a sphere, and shear bands form at an angle of 45° from the poles [1]. For weakly bonded inclusions, interfacial cracks initiate at the pole. These observations have motivated us to analyze deformations and stresses in a particulate composite loaded in tension. It is nearly impossible to find an exact solution of the problem. Here we find an approximate solution by adopting the three phase model of Fröhlich and Sack [2] and Kerner [3] and briefly outlined in the abstract. Kerner analyzed infinitesimal deformations of a composite comprised of elastic spherical inclusions embedded in an elastic matrix and subjected to either a uniform hydrostatic pressure or uniaxial tensile tractions. In the latter case he required that axial elongation and the axial force on a cross-section perpendicular to the axis of loading in the three phase model equal that in a homogeneous body of equivalent elastic moduli. Our analysis is similar to that of Christensen and Lo [4] who considered shear loading, and requires that for the same loads applied on the boundary the strain energy of the equivalent homogeneous elastic body be the same as that of the three phase body. Mackenzie [5] used the three phase model to find elastic constants of an isotropic porous elastic body. The porous body was replaced by a spherical void enclosed in a spherical shell made of the matrix and surrounded by a homogeneous spherical shell of outer radius R and made of an equivalent homogeneous solid material. The mean displacement of the outermost surface of the three phase body was equated to the displacement of the outer surface of a homogeneous spherical

body of radius R and made of the equivalent homogeneous material. The effective moduli derived by Kerner [3], Christensen and Lo [4] and Mackenzie [5] may differ because of different equivalency conditions used.

For a dilute concentration of inclusions, one can approximate stresses at the interfaces of inclusions and the matrix by adopting Eshelby's solution [6] for an inclusion embedded in an infinite elastic medium. However, for finite concentration of inclusions, the interaction among inclusions becomes important. One can use Mori-Tanaka's [7] approach to approximately account for the interaction among inclusions.

ANALYSIS OF THE PROBLEM

1. Formulation

We study infinitesimal deformations of a two-phase composite with each phase made of an isotropic linear elastic material and the body subjected to a uniaxial tensile traction, T , at infinity. We assume that the composite can be modeled as macroscopically homogeneous and isotropic. Furthermore, no separation and sliding occurs between the two phases so that surface tractions and displacements are continuous at their interfaces. In rectangular Cartesian coordinates and with body forces neglected, equations governing their deformations are

$$\sigma_{ij,j}^{(\alpha)} = 0, \quad \alpha = 1, 2; \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^{(1)} n_j^{(1)} = -\sigma_{ij}^{(2)} n_j^{(2)}, \quad u_i^{(1)} = u_i^{(2)}, \quad \text{Eqn. 2}$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^{(\alpha)} = \lambda_\alpha u_{k,k}^{(\alpha)} \delta_{ij} + \mu_\alpha (u_{i,j}^{(\alpha)} + u_{j,i}^{(\alpha)}), \quad \text{Eqn. 3}$$

$$\lim_{|x| \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_{i1} = T \delta_{i1}. \quad \text{Eqn. 4}$$

Here σ_{ij} is the stress tensor, $\sigma_{ij,j} = \partial \sigma_{ij} / \partial x_j$, \mathbf{x} is the position of a material particle, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, a repeated index implies summation over the range of the index, λ and μ are the Lamé constants for the material of a phase, superscript or subscript α indicates the quantity for phase α , \mathbf{u} is the displacement, and \mathbf{n} is an outward unit normal to a surface. Note that equations (2) hold at the interfaces between the inclusions and the matrix. The pertinent boundary condition is given by equation (4).

2. The Three-Phase Model

In order to analyze the problem, we adopt Fröhlich and Sack's [2] idealization of the composite body. The original two-phase composite body is replaced by a two-phase composite sphere embedded in an infinite homogeneous and isotropic medium of unknown effective properties; cf. Fig. 1. The ratio of the radii of the two spheres is such that $a^3 / b^3 = \psi$ where ψ equals the volume fraction of spherical inclusions (phase 2) in the matrix (phase 1). The material moduli of the infinite medium are determined from the requirement that under the same applied surface tractions (4) at infinity, the infinite homogeneous and isotropic medium with no inclusions has the same total strain energy as the 3-phase body of Fig. 1. This requirement combined with Eshelby's [6] solution for the strain energy of a body containing inclusions gives (e.g. see Christensen and Lo [4] for details)

$$\int (\sigma_{rr}^{(0)} u_r^{(c)} + \sigma_{\theta r}^{(0)} u_\theta^{(c)} + \sigma_{\phi r}^{(0)} u_\phi^{(c)}) \sin \theta d\phi d\theta = \int (\sigma_{rr}^{(c)} u_r^{(0)} + \sigma_{\theta r}^{(c)} u_\theta^{(0)} + \sigma_{\phi r}^{(c)} u_\phi^{(0)}) \sin \theta d\phi d\theta \quad \text{Eqn. 5}$$

Figure 1: Equivalent three-phase model.

where quantities with superscript c and zero are respectively for the medium when it contains and does not contain inclusions. These quantities are evaluated at the interface between the matrix and the outer effective homogeneous body.

2.1 A General Solution of the Problem

Substitution from (3) into (1) yields the following Navier's equations: $(\lambda + \mu)u_{k,ki} + \mu u_{i,kk} = 0$, where we have dropped the superscript α for brevity. These imply that $u_{k,k}$ and $u_{i,kk}$ are harmonic functions, i.e., $(u_{k,k})_{,ii} = 0$, $(u_{i,kk})_{,jj} = 0$. For spherical solid harmonic functions ω_n, ϕ_n and $\chi_n (n = \dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots)$ which are rational homogeneous harmonic functions of x_i of positive or negative integral power n , a solution of the Navier equations is (e.g. see section 172 of Love's [8] book and section 95 of Sokolnikoff's [9] book)

$$u_i = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\left(r^2 \omega_{n,i} - 2 \frac{n\lambda + (3n+1)\mu}{(n+3)\lambda + (n+5)\mu} \omega_n \right) + \phi_{n,i} + e_{ijk} x_j \chi_{n,k} \right] \quad \text{Eqn. 6}$$

where $r^2 = x_i x_i$, and e_{ijk} is the permutation symbol; it has values 1 or -1 according as i, j and k form an even or an odd permutation of 1, 2 and 3. By a judicious choice of functions ω_n, ϕ_n and χ_n , one can satisfy boundary conditions (4) and interface continuity conditions (2) at the interfaces $r = a$ and $r = b$. Then the uniqueness theorem of linear elasticity implies that we have the solution of the boundary-value problem defined by equations (1) through (4) to within a rigid body motion.

2.2 Uniaxial Tensile Tractions at Infinity

In order to solve the problem, we take in the inclusion, the matrix, and the effective medium expressions given by equations (7), (8) and (9) respectively.

$$\phi_1 = A_1 r^2 f(\theta), \omega_0 = A_3, \omega_2 = r^2 f(\theta) / 3a^2; \quad \text{Eqn. 7}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 &= B_1 b^3 / r, \phi_2 = 2B_2 b^5 f(\theta) / r^3, \phi_3 = B_4 r^2 f(\theta), \\ \omega_0 &= B_6, \omega_2 = B_5 b^2 r^2 f(\theta) / 3, \omega_{-3} = 2B_3 b^3 f(\theta) / 3r^3; \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eqn. 8}$$

$$\phi_1 = b^3 D_1 / r, \phi_2 = 2D_2 b^5 f(\theta) / r^3, \omega_{-3} = 2D_3 b^3 f(\theta) / 3r^3. \quad \text{Eqn. 9}$$

Here $f(\theta) = (3 \cos^2 \theta - 1)$, A 's, B 's and D 's are nondimensional constants to be determined, and only nonzero functions ϕ_n, ω_n, χ_n are listed. Note that the length b used to non-dimensionalize constants in equations (7), (8) and (9) could be replaced by any other length scale (e.g. a) in the problem. For the infinite homogeneous body containing no inclusions, we take

$$\phi_{-1} = H_1 / r, \phi_{-3} = (H_2 / r^3) f(\theta), \omega_{-3} = H_3 r^2 f(\theta), \quad \text{Eqn. 10}$$

where H_1, H_2 and H_3 are constants.

Substitution from (9) and (10) into (6) and the result into (3) and (4) gives the following for the nonvanishing physical components of the displacement vector and the stress tensor in the infinite homogeneous body:

$$\begin{aligned} u_r^{(0)} &= \frac{Tr}{4\mu_c} \left[\left(\frac{1-v_c}{1+v_c} \right) + \cos 2\theta \right], \quad u_\theta^{(0)} = -\frac{Tr}{4\mu_c} \sin 2\theta, \\ \sigma_{rr}^{(0)} &= \frac{T}{2} (1 + \cos 2\theta), \quad \sigma_{r\theta}^{(0)} = -\frac{T}{2} \sin 2\theta, \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eqn. 11}$$

where $\nu_c = \lambda_c / 2(\lambda_c + \mu_c)$, is Poisson's ratio for the effective homogeneous body. For the three-phase composite body, nonvanishing physical components of displacements and stresses derived from equations (3) and (6) through (9) are given below. In the inclusion,

$$\begin{aligned} u_r^{(1)} &= rA_1 + 2 \left(\frac{\nu_1}{7-4\nu_1} \right) \frac{r^3}{a^2} A_2 + rA_3 + \left[3rA_1 + 6 \left(\frac{\nu_1}{7-4\nu_1} \right) \frac{r^3}{a^2} A_2 \right] \cos 2\theta, \\ u_\theta^{(1)} &= - \left(3rA_1 + \frac{r^3}{a^2} A_2 \right) \sin 2\theta, \\ \frac{\sigma_{rr}^{(1)}}{2\mu_1} &= A_1 - \left(\frac{\nu_1}{7-4\nu_1} \right) \frac{r^2}{a^2} A_2 + \left(\frac{1+\nu_1}{1-2\nu_1} \right) A_3 + \left[3A_1 - 3 \left(\frac{\nu_1}{7-4\nu_1} \right) \frac{r^2}{a^2} A_2 \right] \cos 2\theta, \\ \frac{\sigma_{r\theta}^{(1)}}{2\mu_1} &= - \left[3rA_1 + \left(\frac{7+2\nu_1}{7-4\nu_1} \right) \frac{r^2}{a^2} A_2 \right] \sin 2\theta; \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eqn. 12}$$

in the intermediate matrix,

$$\begin{aligned}
u_r^{(2)} &= -\frac{b^3}{r^3} B_1 - 3\frac{b^5}{r^4} B_2 + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{5-4\nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^2} B_3 + rB_4 + 2 \left(\frac{\nu_2}{7-4\nu_2} \right) \frac{r^3}{b^2} B_5 + rB_6 \\
&+ \left[-9B_2 \frac{b^5}{r^4} + \left(\frac{5-4\nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^2} B_3 + 3rB_4 + 6 \left(\frac{\nu_2}{7-4\nu_2} \right) \frac{r^3}{b^2} B_5 \right] \cos 2\theta, \\
u_\theta^{(2)} &= - \left(6 \frac{b^5}{r^4} B_2 + 2 \frac{b^3}{r^2} B_3 + 3rB_4 + \frac{r^3}{b^2} B_5 \right) \sin 2\theta, \\
\frac{\sigma_{rr}^{(2)}}{2\mu_2} &= 2 \frac{b^3}{r^3} B_1 + 12 \frac{b^5}{r^5} B_2 - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{5-\nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^3} B_3 + B_4 - \left(\frac{\nu_2}{7-4\nu_2} \right) \frac{r^2}{b^2} B_5 + \left(\frac{1+\nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} \right) B_6 \\
&+ \left[36 \frac{b^5}{r^5} B_2 - 2 \left(\frac{5-\nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^3} B_3 + 3B_4 - 3 \left(\frac{\nu_2}{7-4\nu_2} \right) \frac{r^2}{b^2} B_5 \right] \cos 2\theta, \\
\frac{\sigma_{r\theta}^{(2)}}{2\mu_2} &= \left[24 \frac{b^5}{r^5} B_2 - 2 \left(\frac{1+\nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^3} B_3 - 3B_4 - \left(\frac{7+2\nu_2}{7-4\nu_2} \right) \frac{r^2}{b^2} B_5 \right] \sin 2\theta;
\end{aligned}$$

Eqn. 13

and in the effective medium,

$$\begin{aligned}
u_r^{(c)} &= \frac{Tr}{4\mu_c} \left(\frac{1-\nu_c}{1+\nu_c} \right) - \frac{b^3}{r^2} D_1 - 3\frac{b^5}{r^4} D_2 + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{5-4\nu_c}{1-2\nu_c} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^2} D_3 \\
&+ \left[\frac{Tr}{4\mu_c} - 9\frac{b^5}{r^4} D_2 + \left(\frac{5-4\nu_c}{1-2\nu_c} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^2} D_3 \right] \cos 2\theta, \\
u_\theta^{(c)} &= - \left(\frac{Tr}{4\mu_c} + 6\frac{b^5}{r^3} D_2 + 2\frac{b^3}{r^2} D_3 \right) \sin 2\theta, \\
\frac{\sigma_{rr}^{(c)}}{2\mu_c} &= \frac{T}{4\mu_c} + 2\frac{b^3}{r^3} D_1 + 12\frac{b^5}{r^5} D_2 - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{5-\nu_c}{1-2\nu_c} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^3} D_3 \\
&+ \left[\frac{T}{4\mu_c} + 36\frac{b^5}{r^5} D_2 - 2 \left(\frac{5-\nu_c}{1-2\nu_c} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^3} D_3 \right] \cos 2\theta, \\
\frac{\sigma_{r\theta}^{(c)}}{2\mu_c} &= - \left[\frac{T}{4\mu_c} - 24\frac{b^5}{r^5} D_2 + 2 \left(\frac{1+\nu_c}{1-2\nu_c} \right) \frac{b^3}{r^3} \right] \sin 2\theta.
\end{aligned}$$

Eqn. 14

The continuity of displacements and surface tractions at the interfaces $r = a$ and $r = b$ as expressed by equations (2), give twelve equations for the determination of the twelve constants $A_1, A_2, A_3, B_2, \dots, B_6, D_1, D_2$ and D_3 ; these lengthy equations are not listed because of a lack of space.

2.3 Hydrostatic Pressure at Infinity

In order to get one more relation among $\mu_c, \nu_c, \mu_1, \nu_1, \mu_2, \nu_2$ and ψ we study the aforesaid problem with the boundary condition (4) replaced by $\lim_{|x| \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_{ij} = -p_0 \delta_{ij}$, where p_0 is the uniform hydrostatic pressure.

That is, the composite body is subjected to a hydrostatic pressure at infinity. Because of the symmetry of the loading, only the radial component of displacement is nonzero. The radial displacement in the inclusion, the matrix, the effective medium, and the homogeneous body is given by equations (15)₁, (15)₂, (16)₁ and (16)₂ respectively.

$$u_r^{(1)} = Fr, 0 \leq r \leq a; u_r^{(2)} = G_1 r + \frac{G_2}{r^2}, a \leq r \leq b; \quad \text{Eqn. 15}$$

$$u_r^{(c)} = -\frac{p_0}{3\kappa_c} r + \frac{H}{r^2}, b \leq r \leq \infty, u_r^{(0)} = -\frac{p_0}{3\kappa_c} r, 0 \leq r < \infty. \quad \text{Eqn. 16}$$

Here $\kappa_c = \lambda_c + 2\mu_c/3$ is the bulk modulus of the effective medium, and $F, G_1, G_2,$ and H are constants. Using continuity conditions (2) and the energy relation (5), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_c &= \kappa_2 \frac{\beta(1+\gamma\psi) + \gamma(1-\psi)}{\beta(1-\psi) + (\gamma + \psi)}, \quad F = -\frac{p_0}{3\kappa_2} \frac{(1+\gamma)}{\beta(1+\gamma\psi) + \gamma(1-\psi)}, \\ G_1 &= -\frac{p_0}{3\kappa_2} \frac{(\beta + \gamma)}{\beta(1+\gamma\psi) + \gamma(1-\psi)}, \quad G_2 = -\frac{p_0}{3\kappa_2} a^3 \frac{(1-\beta)}{\beta(1+\gamma\psi) + \gamma(1-\psi)}, \quad H = 0, \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eqn. 17}$$

where $\beta = \kappa_1/\kappa_2$, and $\gamma = 4\mu_2/3\kappa_2$. Equation (17) gives $\kappa_c = \kappa_2$ for $\psi = 0$ and $\kappa_c = \kappa_1$ for $\psi = 1$. Thus in the limiting case of no inclusions or no matrix, equation (17)₁ gives exact results.

Note that an explicit expression for ν_c or μ_c can not be easily derived. Furthermore, some of these equations do not hold for $\psi = 0$. Even though numerical results show that for $\psi \rightarrow 0, \nu_c \rightarrow \nu_2$ and for $\psi = 1, \nu_c = \nu_1$, these cannot be readily deduced.

COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL FINDINGS AND RESULTS FROM OTHER THEORIES

1. Comparison of the bulk modulus

Based on Mori-Tanaka's average stress concept and Eshelby's solution for stresses and displacements in an ellipsoidal inclusion embedded in an infinite linear elastic body, Weng [10] derived effective elastic moduli of an anisotropic body equivalent to that of a composite body comprised of a linear elastic matrix containing arbitrarily oriented anisotropic inclusions. For the present case of uniformly distributed spherical inclusions in an isotropic matrix, Weng's equation (5.2) can be simplified to our equation (17)₁. The effective bulk modulus of a porous elastic body deduced from (17)₁ by setting $\kappa_1 = 0$ is given by $\kappa_c = 4\mu_2(1-\psi)/3(\gamma + \psi)$ which, to within terms of order ψ^2 , is the same as that derived by Mackenzie [5] for uniform spherical pores in the body. For rigid inclusions ($\kappa_1 \rightarrow \infty$) embedded in an elastic matrix, equation (17)₁ gives $\kappa_c = \kappa_2 (1 + \gamma\psi)/(1 - \psi)$.

2. Comparison of Young's Modulus and Poisson's Ratio

Christensen and Lo [4] have derived a quadratic equation for the determination of the effective shear modulus; coefficients in this equation are functions of the elastic constants and volume fractions of the constituents. Our equations are too complicated to deduce a closed-form expression for either the effective shear modulus or the effective Young's modulus or the effective Poisson's ratio. Accordingly, we compare computed values of Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio with the test values.

For the tungsten carbide-cobalt (WC - Co) alloy made of WC particles dispersed in Cobalt matrix with material properties listed in Table 1, Fig. 2 compares the variation with the WC volume fraction

Table 1. Material Properties of Constituents

Material	Young's Modulus GPa	Poisson's Ratio	Reference
Cobalt	206.8	0.3	11
Tungsten carbide	703.3	0.22	11
Epoxy	2.5	0.40	9
Silica	74	0.19	9

of Poisson's ratio with the upper and lower bounds of Hashin and Shtrikman [11]. It is clear that results computed from the three-phase model compare very well with the upper bound of Hashin and Shtrikman.

For a composite made of silica particles in an epoxy matrix, Figure 3 compares the effective Young's modulus with the experimental data of Qu and Wong [12]. It is seen that upto 50% volume fraction of silica particles, the computed Young's modulus agrees very well with the test data. For $\psi \geq 0.6$, the computed Young's modulus approaches exponentially Young's modulus for silica as $\psi \rightarrow 1$.

Fig. 2: Comparison of presently computed Poisson's ratio with the Hashin-Shtrikman bounds.

Fig. 3: Comparison of presently computed Young's modulus with the test values.

3. Stress concentration at the interface

For very dilute concentration of particles, there will be practically no interaction among inclusions. Thus deformation fields should correspond to that of a single spherical inclusion embedded in an infinite body. Figure 4 depicts the angular variations of the normalized radial and shear stresses at the interface $r = a$ for different values of the volume fraction ψ of silica particles in an epoxy matrix with material properties listed in Table 1. For $\psi = 0.01$ presently computed stresses match very well with Goodier's [13] solution for a spherical inclusion in an infinite matrix. The tensile radial stress peaks at the pole as expected for the loading considered here. The radial stress is compressive for θ exceeding approximately 65° . It provides an explanation of the experimental observation [1] that interface cracks formed due to dewetting propagate along a great circle in the direction of the equator until $\theta \approx 60^\circ$. Once a crack originates from the pole $\theta = 0^\circ$, our solution becomes invalid since crack surfaces are traction free. Because of the tensile radial stresses in the region $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 65^\circ$, it has been tacitly assumed in our work that the bond between the inclusion and the matrix is strong enough to withstand these tensile stresses. The tendency to debond at the pole increases with an increase in the volume fraction of silica particles.

For $0 \leq \psi \leq 0.3$, the peak value of the shear stress $\sigma_{r\theta}$ occurs at $\theta = 45^\circ$. Variations with ψ of the normalized peak radial and shear stresses are shown in Fig. 5. The peak radial stress increases monotonically with ψ implying thereby that the likelihood of debonding at the pole will increase as the volume fraction of inclusions increases.

Fig. 4: For four values of the volume fraction of inclusions, angular variation of the radial and the shear stress at the inclusion/matrix interface. Filled circles are values at the surface of a single spherical inclusion embedded in an infinite homogeneous medium and subjected to uniaxial tensile tractions at infinity.

Fig. 5: Variation of the maximum radial and the maximum shear stress with the volume fraction of inclusions. As in Fig. 3, the filled circle is the value for a single spherical inclusion.

For ψ greater than say 0.05, stresses plotted in Figs. 4 and 5 should be taken as representative of those at an inclusion/matrix interface. The discrepancy between the actual stresses and those in Figs. 4 and 5 will increase as ψ increases. It can be quantified by solving the problem for the composite numerically (e.g. by the finite element method) but has not been pursued here.

CONCLUSIONS

We have used the three phase model of Fröhlich and Sack to derive effective elastic moduli of a composite comprised of elastic isotropic inclusions embedded in an elastic isotropic matrix. We required that under the same applied surface tractions, an infinite linear elastic isotropic homogeneous body equivalent to the given composite body has the same total strain energy as the three phase body. Our computed bulk modulus agrees with that obtained by Kerner who equated the normal force on any plane surface drawn in the composite to that in the three phase model. The computation of the effective Young's modulus or the effective Poisson's ratio involves the solution of twelve simultaneous algebraic equations. Computed values of these constants are found to match well with the available test data for silica particles in an epoxy matrix. Stresses found at an inclusion/matrix interface qualitatively explain the experimentally observed dewetting/debonding phenomenon.

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